

4- Thiazolidinones. XVII. Mixed 4-Thiazolidinones Derived from N, N'-Diarylthioureas.*

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N,N'-Diarylthioureas condense with monochloroacetic acid in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate to give mixed 4-thiazolidinones. The structure of these compounds has been established by hydrolysing them to the corresponding 2,4-thiazolidinediones and comparing their IR spectra and determining mixed melting points with authentic samples prepared by methods already reported in literature.

4-Thiazolidinones and their derivatives are well known for a number of different types of biological activity¹⁻⁹. The preparation of a number of thiazolidinones having aryl groups such as 3-aryl-2-arylimino-4-thiazolidinones and 2-arylimino-4-thiazolidinones have been reported in literature and their biological activity determined^{10,11}. However, in these compounds the aryl groups are always the same. In search of potential biologically active compounds, it was thought desirable to synthesize mixed 4-thiazolidinones containing different aryl groups at positions 2 and 3 in the ring.

* For other papers in this series, see R. P. Rao, *Chem. Ber.*, 1959, **92**, 2600; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **35**, 576; *Curr. Sc. (India)*, 1966, **35**, 541; *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sc. (India)*, 1960, **29**, 101; 1961, **30**, 179; *Vigyan Parishad Anusandhan Patrika (India)*, 1961, **4**, 19; and the references cited therein.

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This report describes the synthesis of a number of such compounds (I) in which Ar and Ar' are different aryl radicals. A typical reaction is illustrated below :

Structure II for the compound has been proved by hydrolysing it to the corresponding thiazolidinedione (III) and comparing the latter with an authentic sample of 3-*o*-tolyl-2,4-thiazolidinedione prepared by a method already reported in literature¹² from 3-*o*-tolyl-2-*o*-tolylimino-4-thiazolidinone (IV). Cpd. IV was prepared from sym-di-*o*-tolylthiourea and monochloroacetic acid which clearly proves its structure. The reaction sequence is given below :

Mixed melting point determination and comparison of the Ir spectra of the sample of III obtained from II (Ir absorption was at 1655 cm^{-1} and 1730 cm^{-1}) and that obtained from IV clearly proved the structure of III and also established structure of II.

Similarly, all other compounds were prepared and their structures established. In all cases, only one product was formed exclusively, since no other isomer could be isolated from the mother liquor and the TLC runs showed the compounds to be pure. Physical constants and analyses of the new compounds are given in Table I.

EXPERIMENTAL

Infrared spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 137 spectrometer and were taken in KBr disc. All melting points were determined in capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Microanalyses were performed by the Australian Microanalytical Service, Melbourne, Australia.

3-*o*-Tolyl-2-phenylimino-4-thiazolidinone : 3-*o*-Tolyl-1-phenylthiourea (10 g.) and monochloroacetic acid (5 g.) were refluxed in ethanol (50 ml.) for 4.5-5 hr. in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate (4.5 g.) on a water bath. After completion of the reaction, the mixture was

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poured in excess water when a precipitate was obtained. It was filtered, washed several times with hot water, dried and recrystallised from ethanol, yield : 6.5 g. (60%), m.p. 120°. An al. Found : C, 67.67; H, 4.79; N, 10.14. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{14}N_2OS$: C, 68.08; H, 4.96; N, 9.93. The Ir spectrum showed strong carbonyl peak at 1655 cm^{-1} .

TABLE I
Physical constants and analysis of new compounds

Mixed 4-Thiazolidinones			Empirical Formula	M.P. °C	% Carbon	% Hydrogen	% Nitrogen
Cpd. No.	Ar	Ar'					
1. <i>a, b</i>	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	Ph	$C_{16}H_{14}N_2OS$	120	Calc. 68.08 Found 67.67	4.96 4.79	9.93 10.14
2. <i>b, b</i>	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	Ph	$C_{16}H_{14}N_2OS$	149-50	Calc. 68.08 Found 68.12	4.96 5.04	9.93 9.44
3. <i>c, b</i>	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	Ph	$C_{16}H_{14}N_2OS$	125	Calc. 68.08 Found 67.86	4.96 5.10	9.93 9.48
4. <i>d, b</i>	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	Ph	$C_{16}H_{14}N_2O_2S$	93	Calc. 64.43 Found 64.38	4.69 4.69	9.39 8.97
5. <i>e</i>	<i>m</i> -Methoxyphenyl	Ph	$C_{16}H_{14}N_2O_2S$	151	Calc. 64.43 Found 64.46	4.69 4.63	9.39 9.62
6. <i>f</i>	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	Ph	$C_{16}H_{14}N_2O_2S$	78-80	Calc. 64.43 Found 64.35	4.69 4.90	9.39 9.08
7. <i>g</i>	<i>o</i> -Ethoxyphenyl (HCl salt)	Ph	$C_{17}H_{17}N_2O_2SCl$	157	Calc. 58.53 Found 58.76	4.87 4.72	8.03 8.24
8. <i>g</i>	<i>p</i> -Ethoxyphenyl (HCl salt)	Ph	$C_{17}H_{17}N_2O_2SCl$	152	Calc. 58.53 Found 58.31	4.87 4.93	8.03 8.35

(a) On hydrolysis with ethanolic HCl, cpd. 1 gave 3-*o*-Tolyl-2,4-thiazolidinedione, m.p. and mixed¹² m.p. 154°. (b) On hydrolysis, cpd. 2 gave 3-*m*-Tolyl-2,4-thiazolidinedione¹³, m.p. and mixed m.p. 90°. (c) On hydrolysis, cpd. 3 gave 3-*p*-Tolyl-2,4-thiazolidinedione¹⁴, m.p. and mixed m.p. 162°. (d) On hydrolysis, cpd. 4 gave 3-*o*-methoxyphenyl-2,4-thiazolidinedione¹⁵, m.p. and mixed m.p. 113-115°. (e) On hydrolysis, cpd. 5 gave 3-*m*-methoxyphenyl-2,4-thiazolidinedione, m.p. and mixed m.p. 155°. (f) On hydrolysis, cpd. 6 gave 3-*p*-methoxyphenyl-2,4-thiazolidinedione⁶, m.p. and mixed m.p. 160-161°. (g) The structure of compounds 7 and 8 is assumed to be similar to the other structures in view of their resemblance to cpds. 4 and 6 respectively. (h) The Ir spectra of cpds. No. 1, 2, 3 and 4 showed strong carbonyl peaks at 1655 cm^{-1} .

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Hydrolysis of 3-o-Tolyl-2-phenylimino-4-thiazolidinone : A mixture of the above 4-thiazolidinone (1.5 g.), ethanol (15 ml.) and HCl (conc., 3 ml.) was refluxed for 3 to 4 hrs. Ethanol was then distilled and water added. The precipitate was collected, washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol to give 1 g. of pure material, m.p. and mixed m.p. with an authentic sample obtained by the hydrolysis of 3-o-tolyl-2-o-tolylimino-4-thiazolidinone, m.p. 154°.

3-m-Methoxyphenyl-2-m-methoxyphenylimino-4-thiazolidinone : A mixture of sym. di-*m*-methoxyphenylthiourea (10 g.), monochloroacetic acid (5 g.), anhydrous sodium acetate (5 g.) and ethanol (80 ml.) was refluxed for 5 hrs. Afterwards the contents were poured in excess water when a precipitate was obtained, which was filtered, washed several times with boiling water, dried and finally recrystallised from ethanol; yield, 9.3 g. (85%), m.p. 160°. Anal. Found : C, 62.15; H, 4.90; N, 8.72. Calc. for $C_{17}H_{16}N_2O_3S$: C, 62.19; H, 4.87; N, 8.53.

Hydrolysis of 3-m-methoxyphenyl-2-m-methoxyphenylimino-4-thiazolidinone : It was carried out in the same manner as that reported for 3-o-tolyl-2-phenylimino-4-thiazolidinone (see above). Working up as usual gave 3-m-methoxyphenyl-2,4-thiazolidinedione in 80 per cent yield, m.p. 155°. Anal. Found : C, 54.00; H, 4.34; N, 6.19. Calc. for $C_{10}H_9NO_3S$: C, 53.81; H, 4.03; N, 6.27. The Ir spectrum showed twin peaks at 1730 cm^{-1} and 1658 cm^{-1} , in the carbonyl region.

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